

A systematic and synonymic list of the HesperIIDae of Western Palearctic butterflies hyperlinked to the original descriptions (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea)

Submitted: 14.xi.2025 | Accepted: 08.xii.2025 | Published online: 30.xii.2025.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17793560](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17793560)

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Abstract

A systematic and synonymic list of the HesperIIDae butterflies of the Western Palearctic is presented, with all names hyperlinked to their original descriptions. The work covers taxonomic hierarchy from family to species level, incorporating historical synonyms, typification details, and bibliographic references, providing a comprehensive and navigable tool for lepidopterists and taxonomists.

Key words

HesperIIDae — Papilionoidea — Lepidoptera — Western Palearctic — taxonomy — nomenclature — synonymy — systematic catalogue — type species — original descriptions — type locality — butterfly classification — historical entomology.

Introduction

The family HesperIIDae comprises groups of species with a remarkably similar habitus, making species identification often challenging. Identification frequently requires examination of the genitalia (e.g., in the genus *Pyrgus*), and in some cases genetic analysis is necessary, for instance to distinguish *Spialia rosae* Hernández-Roldán et al., 2016.

Research on species within this family has long been neglected due to these identification difficulties. Whether owing to scarce material or simple oversight, early authors frequently confused species or grouped several taxa under a single name, resulting in a chaotic classification of the group. Linnaeus described only three species for the European fauna, and his successors made little progress. It was not until Rambur (1839), who described seven new *Pyrgus* species in the same publication, that a coherent outline of the European HesperIIDae fauna began to emerge.

HesperIIDae were traditionally assigned to the superfamily Hesperioidea. The reclassification of the family within Papilionoidea was proposed following significant advances in molecular phylogenetics over the past two decades, as reported by Warren *et al.* (2009) and subsequent studies.

For the Western Palearctic fauna, the implications of these studies remain limited, yet they can occasionally prompt substantial reorganisation within certain groups, such as *Carcharodus*. It is therefore crucial to monitor the current literature closely and to integrate these findings into the systematics of Western Palearctic species.

Regularly updating a comprehensive systematic and synonymic reference list is therefore essential. A dynamic, continuously maintained list offers clear advantages over fixed, paper-based publications, which cannot be revised once issued and may become outdated relatively quickly as new taxonomic findings emerge.

Family

HesperIIDae Latreille, 1809

[ICZN] Hesperides Latreille, 1809. Gen. Crust. Ins. 4: [187](#), [207](#).

TG: *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793.

[JS] Diorthosia Rafinesque, 1815. Analyse Nat.: [128](#).

TG: *Diorthosus* Rafinesque, 1815.

[RJ] Erynnidae Hampson, 1918. Novit. Zool. 25: [386](#).

TG: *Erynnis* Schrank, 1801 ; name rejected by ICZN – Case 3749, Bull. Zool. Nomencl. 75(1): 130-134.

- [JH] Hesperidae Westwood, 1840. *Introd. Modern Class. Ins.* 2: [360](#).
TG: *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793.
- [NN] Urbicolae (Fabr.) Scudder, 1872. *Report Peabody Acad. Sci.* 1872: [46](#).
TG: *Urbicola* Linnaeus, 1758.
- [ICZN] Hesperidae Latreille, 1809. In *Opinion 1240* (ICZN, 1983. *Bull. Zool. Nomencl.* 40(1): [27-28](#).
TG: *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793.

Subfamily

Heteropterinae Aurivillius, 1925

- [ORIG] Heteropterinae Aurivillius, 1925. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmet. *Erde* 13: [506](#), [546](#).
TG: *Heteropterus* Duméril, 1806.
- [IN] Eumesiidae Felder & Felder, [1867]. *Reise Öst. Fregatte Novara, Zool.* 2(2): 504 (invalid by ICZN, opinion 1669).
TG: *Eumesia* Felder & Felder, [1867] (invalid by ICZN, opinion 1669).
- [?] Cyclopidinae Speyer, 1879. *Entomol. Ztg.* 40(10-12): [486](#).
TG: *Cyclopides* Hübner, [1819] (= *Heteropterus* Duméril, 1806).
- [JS] Carterocephalini Orfila, 1949. *Acta Zool. Lilloana* 8: 584.
TG: *Carterocephalus* Lederer, 1852.

Tribe

Heteropterini Aurivillius, 1925

- [ORIG] Heteropterinae Aurivillius, 1925. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmet. *Erde* 13: [506](#), [546](#).
TG: *Heteropterus* Duméril, 1806.
- [JS] Carterocephalini Orfila, 1949. *Acta Zool. Lilloana* 8: 584.
TG: *Carterocephalus* Lederer, 1853.

Genus

Heteropterus Duméril, 1806

- [ORIG] *Heteropterus* Duméril, 1806. *Zool. analyt.*: [271](#).
TS: *Papilio aracinthus* Fabricius, 1777 (= *P. morpheus* Pallas, 1771) by subsequent designation by Hemming, 1934. *Gen. names Holarct. Butt.* 1: 167.
- [JS] *Cyclopides* Hübner, [1819]. *Verz. Bekannt. Schmett.* (7): [111](#).
TS: *Papilio steropes* [D. & Schiff.], 1775 (= *P. morpheus* Pallas, 1771) by subsequent designation by Butler, 1870. *Entomol. Month. Mag.* 2: [96](#).

Heteropterus morpheus (Pallas, 1771)

- [ORIG] *Papilio (Plebeius urbicola) morpheus* Pallas, 1771. *Reise verschied. Prov. russ. Reichs* 1: [471](#).
TL: Samara region (Russia Federation).
- [JS] *Papilio (Plebejus Urbicola) speculum* Rottemburg, 1775. *Naturforscher* 6: [31](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Papilio (Plebejus Urbicola) steropes* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. *Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.*: [160](#).
TL: Vienna area (Austria).

- [JS] *Papilio (Plebejus Urbicola) aracinthus* Fabricius, 1777. Gen. Ins.: [271-272](#).
TL: Austria.
- [JS] *Papilio speculifer* Geoffroy, 1785. Entomol. Paris. 2: [246](#).
TL: Paris (France).
- [JS] *Heteropterus morpheus aniensis* Dannehl, 1925. Entomol. Z. 39(20): [82](#).
TL: Monti Sabini (C Italy).
- [JS] *Heteropterus morpheus* race *minutus* Lempke, 1936. Tijdschr. Entomol. 79(3-4): [310](#).
TL: Maaseyck (NE Belgium).
- [JS] *Heteropterus morpheus* var. *aquitainensis* Pionneau, 1938. Misc. Entomol. 39(6): [50](#).
TL: Bois de Pessac (SW France).
- [JS] *Heteropterus morpheus* race *vasconiae* Picard, 1948. Rev. Fr. Lépidop. 11(15-16): 327.
TL: Biarritz (SW France).
- [IFS] *Heteropterus morpheus* f.[=ab.] *maculata* Schwingenschuss, 1952. Z. Wien. Entomol. Ges. 37: [131](#).
TL: Herzogenburg (Austria).
- [IFS] *Heteropterus morpheus* f.[=ab.] *luxurians* Lempke, 1953. Tijdschr. Entomol. 96(4): [251](#).
TL: Empe (Netherlands).
- [JS] *Heteropterus morpheus post-morpheus* Floriani, 1968. Boll. Soc. Entomol. It. 98: 118.
TL: Merlino (Lombardia, N Italy).
- [JS] *Heteropterus morpheus* ssp. *stangellaieri* Aitsleitner & Gros, 2019. Entomofauna 40: [300](#), [Abb. 1-2](#).
TL: Val Cellina, Claut-Contron (Pordenone prov., NE Italy).

Genus

Carterocephalus Lederer, 1853

- [ORIG] *Carterocephalus* Lederer, 1852. Verh. zool.-bot. Ver. Wien 2(Abhandl.): [26](#).
TS: *Papilio paniscus* Fabricius, 1775 (= *P. palaemon* Pallas, 1771) by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1875. Proc. Am. Acad. Arts Sci 10: [134](#).
- [JS] *Aubertia* Oberthür, 1896. Étud. entomol. 20: [40](#).
TS: *Aubertia dulcis* Oberthür, 1896 (= *C. christophi* Gr.-Grsh., 1891) by subsequent designation by Lindsey, 1925. Ann. entomol. Soc. Am. 18(1): [79](#).
- [JS] *Pamphilida* Lindsey, 1925. Ann. entomol. Soc. Am. 18(1): [95](#).
TS: *Papilio palaemon* Pallas, 1771 by original designation.

Carterocephalus silvicola (Meigen, [1829])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia silvicola* Meigen, [1829]. Syst. Besch. eur. Schmett. 2: [65-66](#), [pl. 55](#), [fig. 7a-d](#).
TL: Braunschweig (Lower Saxony, Germany).
- [JH] *Papilio (Plebejus Urbicola) silvius* Knoch, 1781. Beitr. Insektengesch. 1: [71-73](#), [pl. 5](#), [fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Leipzig (E Germany) ; nec *Papilio sylvius* Poda, 1761. Ins. Mus. Graec.: [77](#).

Carterocephalus palaemon Pallas, 1771

- [ORIG] *Papilio (Plebeius urbicola) palaemon* Pallas, 1771. Reise verschied. Prov. russ. Reichs 1: [471](#).
TL: Akhtushka river (Samara obl., Russian Federation).

- [JS] *Papilio (Plebejus Urbicola) paniscus* Fabricius, 1775. Syst. entomol.: [531](#).
TL: Leipzig (E Germany).
- [JS] *Papilio (Plebejus Urbicola) brontes* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ank. syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienerg.: [160](#).
TL: Vienna area (Austria).
- [JS] *Carterocephalus palaemon* var. *albiguttata* Christoph, 1893. Dt. entomol. Z. 6(1): [87-88](#).
TL: Vilui, Irkut, Guberli, Ural merid. (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Pamphila palaemon* var. *freyi* Hellweger, 1911. Jahresb. Privat-Gymn. Brixen 36: 71.
TL: Wetterstein, Haller Salzberg (Austria).
- [JS] *Pamphila palaemon silvioides* Muller, 1920. Verh. Zool.-Bot. Ges. Wien 70: (52).
TL: Rekawinkel (Austria).
- [JS] *Pamphila palaemon* ssp. *borealis* Lingonblad, 1945. Notulae Entomol. 24: [71-75, fig.](#)
TL: Vasa (Ostrobothnia prov. Finland).
- [JS] *Carterocephalus palaemon* ssp. *tollii* Krzywicki, 1967. Ann. zool., Warsz. 25(1): 119-121, 150-152, pl. 28, fig. 1-23, pl. 29, fig. 11-12.
TL: Puszcza Białawieska (Poland).
- [JH] *Carterocephalus palaemon* ssp. *sarahe* Gastón Ortíz & Gómez Bustillo, 1974. SHILAP 3(9): [64-66, fig.](#)
TL: Peña de Orduña (Vizcaya prov., Spain).

Subfamily

Hesperiinae Latreille, 1809

- [ORIG] Hesperides Latreille, 1809. Gen. Crust. Ins. 4: [187, 207](#).
TS: *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793.
- [JS] Pamphilinae Butler, 1871. Entomol. Monthly Mag. 7: [56](#).
TS: *Pamphila* Fabricius 1807.
- [ICZN] Hesperidae Latreille, 1809. In Opinion 1240 (ICZN, 1983. Bull. Zool. Nomencl. 40(1): [27-28](#).
TS: *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793.

Tribe

Baorini Doherty, 1886

- [ORIG] Baorinae Doherty, 1886. J. Asiat. Soc. Bengal. 55(2): [107, 111](#).
TG: *Baoris* Moore, 1881.
- [JS] Gegenini Chou, 1994. Zhongguo die lei zhi 1: 14, 88.
TG: *Gegenes* Hübner, [1819].
- [JS] Parnarini Koçak & Seven, 1997. Priamus 9(2-3): [102, 110](#).
TG: *Parnara* Moore, [1881].
- [JS] Parnarina Koçak & Seven, 1997. Priamus 9(2-3): [110](#).
TG: *Parnara* Moore, [1881].
- [JS] Itonina Koçak & Seven, 1997. Priamus 9(2-3): [110](#).
TG: *Iton* Nicéville, 1895.

Genus

Pelopidas Walker, 1870

[ORIG] *Pelopidas* Walker, 1870. Entomologist 5(76): [56](#).

TS: *Pelopidas midea* Walker, 1870 by monotypy.

[JS] *Chapra* Moore, [1881]. Lepid. Ceylon 1(4): [169](#).

TS: *Hesperia mathias* Fabricius, 1798 by original designation.

Pelopidas thrax (Hübner, [1821])

[ORIG] *Gegenes thrax* Hübner, [1821]. Samml. exot. Schmett. 2: [pl. \[150\], fig. 1-4](#).

TL: Syria (?).

[JS] *Pelopidas midea* Walker, 1870. Entomologist 5(76): [56](#).

TL: Cairo (Egypt).

Genus

Borbo Evans, 1949

[ORIG] *Borbo* Evans, 1949. Catal. Hesp. Eur. Asia Austr. Brit. Mus.: [44](#), [436](#).

TS: *Hesperia borbonica* Boisduval, 1833 by original designation.

Borbo borbonica (Boisduval, 1833)

[ORIG] *Hesperia borbonica* Boisduval, 1833. Nouv. Ann. Mus. Hist. nat. 2(2): [213-214](#).

TL: Réunion (Overseas department, France).

[JS] *Hesperia zelleri* Lederer, 1855. Verh. Zool.-Bot. Ges. Wien 5(Abhandl.): [194](#).

TL: Syria.

[JS] *Pamphila borbonica holli* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. Lépid. Comp. 4: [363-365](#).

TL: Hussein Dey (Algeria).

[NN] *Borbo zelleri tarraconensis* Meliá & Gómez-Bustillo, 1974. Marip. Peníns. Ibér. 2: 31.

TL: Amposta (Tarragona prov., NE Spain).

Genus

Gegenes Hübner, [1819]

[ORIG] *Gegenes* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [107](#).

TL: *Papilio pumilio* Hoffman[n]segg, 1804 by subsequent designation by Opinion 827 (ICZN, 1967. Bull. Zool. Nomencl. 24 : 226-227).

[JS] *Philoodus* Rambur, [1842]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2(5): 308.

Hesperia nostradamus Fabricius, 1793 by subsequent designation by Scudder, 1875. Proc. Am. Acad. Arts Sci 10: [248](#).

Gegenes pumilio (Hoffman[n]segg, 1804)

[ORIG] *Papilio pumilio* Hoffman[n]segg, 1804. Mag. Insektenk. 3: [202](#).

TL: Amalfi (Salerno prov., Italy).

[JH] *Papilio (Plebejus Urbicola) pygmaeus* Cyrillo, [1791]. Entomol. Neapol.: [pl. 5, fig. 5](#).

TL: Naples (S Italy) ; *nec* Fabricius, 1775. Syst. entomol.: [536](#).

- [JS] *Hesperia aetna* Boisduval, 1840. Gen. Ind. Meth. Eur. Lepid.: [35](#).
TL: Sicily (S Italy).
- [JS] *Philoodus lefebvrei* Rambur, [1842]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2(5): 308.
TL: Sicily (S Italy).
- [JS] *Gegenes pumilio* ssp. *balearica* Fernández Vidal, 1987. SHILAP 15(60): [346-347, fig.](#)
TL: Bunyola (Mallorca, Islas Baleares, Spain).

Gegenes nostradamus (Fabricius, 1793)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia nostradamus* Fabricius, 1793. Entomol. Syst. 3(1): [328-329](#).
TL: NW Africa (Algeria).
- [JS] *Pamphila proclea* Walker, 1870. Entomologist 5: [56](#).
TL: Cairo (Egypt).
- [JS] *Gegenes nostradamus* race *pumilionimina* Verity, 1931. Boll. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 63(6-7): 111.
TL: Viareggio, Lucca (Tuscany, Italy).

Tribe

Hesperiini Latreille, 1809

- [ORIG] Hesperides Latreille, 1809. Gen. Crust. Ins. 4: [187, 207](#).
TG: *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793.
- [JH] Hesperidae Westwood, 1840. Introd. Modern Class. Ins. 2: [360](#).
TG: *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793.
- [JS] Thymelicinae Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [90](#).
TG: *Thymelicus* Hübner, [1819].

Genus

Ochlodes Scudder, 1872

- [ORIG] *Ochlodes* Scudder, 1872. Report Peabody Acad. Sci. 1872: [57](#).
TL: *Hesperia nemorum* Boisduval, 1852 (= *Hesperia agricola* Boisduval, 1852) by original description.

Ochlodes sylvanus (Esper, 1777)

- [ORIG] *Papilio* (*Plebeius Urbicola*) *sylvanus* Esper, 1777. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(1): pl. 36 (suppl. 12), fig. 1 ; [1779]: [343](#).
TL: Franconia (N Bavaria, Germany) ; see Opinion 1944 (ICZN, 2000. Bull. Zool. Nomencl. 57(1): [56-57](#)).
- [JH] *Papilio* (*Plebeius Urbicola*) *melicerta* Bergsträsser, 1780. Nom. Ins. 4: [38, pl. 90, fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Germany ; *nec* Drury, 1773. Illustr. Nat. Hist. 2: [34, pl. 19, fig. 3-4, index \[1\]](#).
- [JS] [*Hesperia*] *anatolica* Plötz, 1883. Entomol. Ztg. 44: [219](#).
TL: Turkey.
- [JS] *Hesperia hyrcana* Christoph, 1893. Dt. Entomol. Z. 6(1): [87](#).
TL: Lenkoran (Azerbaijan), Astrabad (Iran).
- [JS] *Augiades faunus* Turati, 1905. Nat. Sicil. 18(2-3): [36-38, pl. 6, fig. 5, 9](#).
TL: Gavarnie (France).

- [JS] *Augiades sylvanus* var. *norvegica* Tutt, 1905. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [135](#).
TL: Saeterstoen (Norway).
- [JS] *Adopaea sylvanus alpina* Hoffmann & Klos, 1914. Mitt. Naturwiss. Ver. Steiermark 50: [314](#).
TL: Krieglach (Austria).
- [JS] *Augiades (Erynnis) sylvanus* f. *sylvanellus* Turati, 1915. Atti Soc. Ital. Sci. Nat. 53(3-4): 603.
TL: Italy.
- [JS] *Augiades sylvanus* race *septentrionalis* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [28](#).
TL: England.
- [JS] *Augiades sylvanus taurica* Gaede, 1931. In: Seitz, Gross-Schmet. Erde (1)1(suppl.): [322](#), pl. 16k, fig. [10-11].
TL: England.
- [JS] *Ochlodes venata alexandra* Hemming, 1934. Stylops 3(5): [99](#), [200](#).
TL: Nom. nov. pro *Papilio sylvanus*, Esper, 1777 (invalid, homonym of *Papilio sylvanus*, Drury, 1773) ; see Opinion [1944](#) (ICZN, 2000).
- [JS] *Augiades sylvanus esperi* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(5, suppl.): [13](#).
TL: Nom. nov. pro *Papilio sylvanus*, Esper, 1777 (invalid, homonym of *Papilio sylvanus*, Drury, 1773) ; see Opinion [1944](#) (ICZN, 2000).
- [JS] *Augiades sylvanus* ssp. *nicaeensis* Praviel, 1948. Rev. Fr. Lépidop. 11(15-16): 324.
TL: Alpes-Maritimes (SE France).
- [JS] *Ochlodes venatum* race *concoulensis* Picard, 1948. Lambillionea 48(5-6): 41.
TL: Gard (France).
- [JS] *Ochlodes venatum* f. *pseudonicaeense* Kauffmann, 1951. Mitt. Schweiz Entomol. Ges. 24(4): [373](#).
TL: S Tessin, ... (Switzerland)
- [JS] *Ochlodes venatum hesperodoron* Kauffmann, 1956. Entomol. Z. 66(5): 54.
TL: Europe.

Genus

Hesperia Fabricius, 1793

- [ORIG] *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793. Entomol. Syst. 3(1): [258](#).
TS: *Papilio comma* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Dalman, 1816. K. svenska Vetensk.-Akad. Handl. 1816: [200-201](#).
- [JS] *Pamphila* Fabricius, 1807. In Illiger, Mag. Insektenk. 6: [287](#).
TS: *Papilio comma* Linnaeus, 1758 by subsequent designation by Westwood, 1840. Introd. Mod. Classif. Ins. 2(synopsis): [88](#).
- [JS] *Diorthosus* Rafinesque, 1815. Analyse Nat.: [128](#).
TS: *Papilio comma* Linnaeus, 1758 (ICZN Code art. 67.8 - replacement name for *Hesperia* Cuvier, 1800).
- [JS] *Phidias* Rafinesque, 1815. Analyse Nat.: [128](#).
TS: *Papilio comma* Linnaeus, 1758 (ICZN Code art. 67.8 - replacement name for *Pamphila* Fabricius, 1807).
- [JH] *Symmachia* Sodoffsky, 1837. Bull. Soc. Nat. Mosc. 10(6): [82](#).
TS: *Papilio comma* Linnaeus, 1758 (ICZN Code art. 67.8 - replacement name for *Hesperia* Fabricius, 1793) ; *nec Symmachia* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [25-26](#).
- [JS] *Ocytes* Scudder, 1872. 4th Ann. Rep. Peabody Acad. Sci. (1871): [76](#).
TS: *Hesperia metea* Scudder, 1863 by original designation.
- [JS] *Anthomaster* Scudder, 1872. 4th Ann. Rep. Peabody Acad. Sci. (1871): [78](#).
TS: *Hesperia leonardus* Harris, 1862 by original designation.
- [JS] *Urbicola* (Linnaeus): Tutt, 1905. Nat. Hist. Brit. Butt. 8(1): [84](#).

TS: *Papilio comma* Linnaeus, 1758 by original designation.

Hesperia comma (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio (Plebejus urbicola) comma* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [484](#).
TL: Sweden.
- [JS] *Papilio virgula* Retzius, 1783. Gen. Spec. Ins.: [31](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Hesperia comma* var. *catena* Staudinger, 1861. Entomol. Ztg. 22: [357](#).
TL: Lappland (Sweden).
- [JS] *Hesperia comma* var. *alpina* Harcourt-Bath, 1896. Entomologist 29(392): [21](#).
TL: Wengern-Scheideck Pass (Bern, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Augiades comma* var. *pallida* Staudinger, 1901. In Staudinger & Rebel, Cat. Lepid. pal. Fauneng.: [92](#).
TL: Turkey.
- [JS] *Augiades comma* var. *apennina* Rostagno, 1911. In: Rostagno & Zapelloni, Boll. Soc. Zool. Ital. (2)12(1-4): [10-11](#).
TL: Lazio (C Italy).
- [JS] *Augiades benuncas* Oberthür, 1912. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 1912(16): [349-351](#).
TL: Lambèse (Algeria).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *aurata* Verity, 1924. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 36(7/8): [107](#).
TL: Abetone (Tuscany, Italy).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *orae* Verity, 1924. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 36(7/8): [107](#).
TL: Pertusola, Gulf of Spezia (Liguria, Italy).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *galliaemeridiei* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 33(7): [124-125](#).
TL: Nîmes (Gard, S France).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *hibera* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 33(7): [125](#).
TL: Albarracin (Aragon, Spain).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *alpapennina* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 33(7): [125](#).
TL: Bolognola, Mts Sibillini (Italy).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *alpiumflava* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 33(7): [125-126](#).
TL: Bolzano (NE Italy).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *macrocomma* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 33(7): [126-127](#).
TL: Valdieri (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *superalpina* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 33(7): [127](#).
TL: Stelvio, Vallée de Bornio (N Italy).
- [JS] *Urbicola comma* race *altralpina* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 33(7): [127](#).
TL: Haut de la route du Stelvio, Sulden, Ortler (N Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia comma* race *hemipallida* Verity, 1940. Farf. Dirne Ital. 1: 116, pl. 4, fig. 66-69.
TL: Madonie (Sicily, S Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia comma* race *maroccana* Picard, 1950. Bull. Soc. Sci. Nat. Maroc 28: [129-130](#).
TL: Afraou des Beni Abdallah (Moyen Atlas, Morocco).

Genus

Thymelicus Hübner, [1819]

[ORIG] *Thymelicus* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [113](#).

TG: *Papilio actaeon* Esper (= *Papilio acteon* Rott., 1775) by subsequent designation by Butler, 1870. Entomol. Month. Mag. 7: [94](#).

[JS] *Adopoea* Billberg, 1820. Enum. Ins. Mus. Billb.: [81](#).

TG: *Papilio linea* Müller, 1766 (= *Papilio sylvestris* Poda, 1761) by monotypy.

[JS] *Pelion* Kirby, 1858. List Brit. Rhop.: [\[3\]](#).

TG: *Papilio linea* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775 (= *Papilio sylvestris* Poda, 1761) by original designation.

[IS] *Thymelinus* Stephens, [1835]. Illustr. Brit. Entomol. 4: [405](#).

Incorrect subsequent spelling of *Thymelicus* Hübner, [1819].

Thymelicus christi Rebel, 1894

[ORIG] *Thymelicus christi* Rebel, 1894. Ann. Naturhist. Hofmus. 9(1): [41-42](#), [pl. 1, fig. 2](#).

TL: Tenerife (Canary Islands, Spain).

Thymelicus acteon (Rottemburg, 1775)

[ORIG] *Papilio (Plebejus Urbicola) acteon* Rottemburg, 1775. Naturforscher 6: [30-31](#).

TL: Landsberg an der Warthe, current city of Gorzów Wielkopolski (Lubuskie prov., Poland).

[JH] *Papilio actaeon* [sic] Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 96, fig. 488-490](#), [1806]: [73](#).

Incorrect subsequent spelling of *Papilio acteon* Rottemburg, 1775.

[CN] *Thymelicus actaeon* [sic] Hübner, [1819]. Verz. Bekannt. Schmett.(7): [113](#).

Comb. nov. for *Papilio acteon* Rottemburg, 1775.

[JS] *Thymelicus heydeni* Plötz, 1884. Entomol. Ztg. 45(7-9): [285](#).

TL: Syria [?].

[IFS] *Thymelicus actaeon* ab. *virescens* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [118](#).

TL: United Kingdom.

[IFS] *Thymelicus acteaon* ab. *clara* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [119](#).

TL: Grésy-sur-Aix (Haute-Savoie dep., E France).

[IFS] *Thymelicus actaeon* ab. *obsoleta* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [119](#).

TL: -.

[IFS] *Thymelicus actaeon* ab. *extensa* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [119](#).

TL: Chavoire (Haute-Savoie dep., E France).

[JS] *Thymelicus actaeon* race *ragusai* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [28](#).

TL: Palermo, S. Martino alle Scale (Sicily, S Italy).

[JS] *Thymelicus (Adopaea) acteon* race *obsoleta* Tutt: Turner, 1920. Trans. entomol. Soc. Lond. 1920(1/2): [206](#).

Stat. nov. for *Thymelicus acteon* ab. *obsoleta* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [119](#).

[JS] *Thymelicus (Adopaea) acteon* f. *clara-obsoleta* Turner, 1920. Trans. entomol. Soc. Lond. 1920(1/2): [206](#).

TL: Cyprus.

[JS] *Thymelicus (Adopaea) acteon* ssp. *phoenix* Graves, 1925. Trans. entomol. Soc. Lond. 73(1/2): [44-45, pl. 5, fig. 6-7](#).

TL: Jemhur-Areya, Beirut (Lebanon).

- [SR] *Thymelicus actaeon* race *clara* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 103-104, pl. 4, fig. 36-37.
Stat. rev. for *Thymelicus actaeon* ab. *clara* Tutt, 1906.
- [SR] *Thymelicus actaeon* race *aurescens* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 103-104, pl. 4, fig. 36-37.
Stat. rev., replacement name for *Thymelicus actaeon* ab. *clara* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [119](#).
- [JS] *Thymelicus actaeon* race *pulchractaeon* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 104, pl. 4, fig. 40-42.
TL: Gran Sasso (Abruzzo, C Italy).
- [SR] *Thymelicus actaeon* race *virescens* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 105, pl. 4, fig. 43-45.
Stat. rev. for *Thymelicus actaeon* ab. *virescens* Tutt, 1906.
- [JS] *Thymelicus actaeon* [sic] ssp. *orana* Evans, 1949. Cat. Hesp. Eur. Asia Austr. Brit. Mus.: [345](#).
TL: Morocco, Algeria.
- [JS] *Thymelicus actaeon* race *maurus* Picard, 1948. Bull. Soc. Sci. nat. Maroc 28: [126-127](#).
TL: Casablanca (Morocco).

Thymelicus hamza (Oberthür, 1876)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia hamza* Oberthür, 1876. Étud. Entomol. 1: 28-29, pl. 3, fig. 2a-c.
TL: Oran (Algeria).
- [JS] *Adopaea* (*Thymelicus*) *novissima* Turati, 1921. Atti Soc. Ital. Sci. Nat. 60: [221-225, fig.](#)
TL: Al Fuehat (Libya).

Thymelicus hyrax (Lederer, 1861)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia hyrax* Lederer, 1861. Wiener entomol. Monatschr. 5(5): [149-150, pl. 1, fig. 6](#).
TL: Antioch, current city of Antakya (Hatay prov., Turkey).
- [JS] *Adopaea* [sic] *pfeifferi* Bytinski-Salz & Brandt, 1937. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 49(suppl.): [\(2\)-\(3\)](#).
TL: Al Fuehat (Libya).

Thymelicus sylvestris (Poda, 1761)

- [ORIG] *Papilio sylvestris* Poda, 1761. Ins. Mus. Graec.: [79](#).
TL: Graz (Austria).
- [JS] *Papilio flava* Brünnich, 1763. In: Pontoppidan, Danske Atlas 1: [685, pl. 30, fig.\[2\]](#).
TL: Denmark.
- [JS] *Papilio thaumas* Hufnagel, 1766. Berlin. Mag. 2(1): [62-63](#).
TL: Berlin (Germany).
- [JS] *Papilio linea* Müller, 1766. In: Allioni, Misc. Taurin. 3: [192](#).
TL: Turin (Italy).
- [JS] *P[apilio]. flavus* Müller, 1776. Zool. Dan. Prodr.: [115](#).
TL: Denmark.
- [JS] *P[apilio]. divaricatus* Geoffroy, 1785. Entomol. Paris. 2: [246-247](#).
TL: Paris (France).
- [JS] *Papilio venula* Hübner, [1813]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 131, fig. 666-669](#), 1824: [6](#).
TL: Germany.

- [JS] *Adopaea flava* var. *syriaca* Tutt, 1905. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [107](#).
TL: Syria.
- [IFS] *Adopaea flava* ab. *iberica* Tutt, 1905. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [107](#).
TL: Canales, Moncayo, Bejar, ... (Spain).
- [IFS] *Adopaea flava* ab. *major* Tutt, 1905. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [107](#).
TL: Villach, ... (Austria).
- [SR] *Adopaea flava* race *iberica* Verity, 1920. Boll. Lab. Zool. Portici 14: [43](#).
Stat rev. for *Adopaea flava* ab. *iberica* Tutt, 1905..
- [NN] *Adopaea flava* race *macta* Verity, 1926. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 38(7/8): [104](#).
Nom. nov. and Stat. rev. for *Adopaea flava* ab. *major* Tutt, 1905.
- [JS] *Adopaea flava* ssp. *fulminans* Rebel & Zerny, [1932]. Denkschr. Akad. Wiss. Wien 103: [83](#), pl. 1, fig. 3-4.
TL: Kula e Lumës (Albania).
- [JS] *Adopaea flava* race *maxima* Verity, 1936. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 48(suppl.): [\(3\)-\(4\)](#).
TL: Thessaloniki (N Greece).
- [JS] *Adopaea flava* var. *werneri* Rebel, 1937. Z. Öst. Entomol. Ver. 22(7): [66](#).
TL: Kifissia (Attica, C Greece).
- [ND] *Thymelicus sylvester* ff. *claricantes* Kauffmann, [1953]. Boll. Soc. Ticin. Sci. Nat. 47/48: [11](#).
Nom. nud., stat. of 'ff' ?
- [ND] *Thymelicus sylvester* ff. *nigricantes* Kauffmann, [1953]. Boll. Soc. Ticin. Sci. Nat. 47/48: [11](#).
Nom. nud., stat. of 'ff' ?

Thymelicus lineola (Ochsenheimer, 1808)

- [ORIG] *Papilio lineola* Ochsenheimer, 1808. Schmett. Eur. 1(2): [230-231](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JH] *Papilio virgula* Hübner, [1813]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 130, fig. 660-663](#), 1824: [5](#).
TL: Germany ; *nec* Retzius, 1783. Gen. Spec. Ins.: [31](#)..
- [JS] *Pamphila ludoviciae* Mabille, 1883. Ann. Soc. entomol. Belg. 27(suppl.): [lxviii-lxix](#).
TL: Murat (Auvergnés, France), Pyrénées (France).
- [JS] *Thymelicus lineola* var. *semicolon* Staudinger, 1892. Dt. Entomol. Z. Iris 5(2): [282](#).
TL: Lambèse (Algeria).
- [IFS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* ab. *clara* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [96](#).
TL: Larche (SE France).
- [IFS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* ab. *major* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [96](#).
TL: Wolfsberg (Austria).
- [IFS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* ab. *major-clara* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [96](#).
TL: Tragacete (Spain).
- [IFS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* ab. *intermedia* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [96](#).
TL: Macugnaga (N Italy).
- [SR] *Thymelicus lineola* ssp. *major-clara* Graves, 1925. Trans. entomol. Soc. Lond. 73(1/2): [42-43](#).
Stat. rev. for *Adopaea lineola* ab. *major-clara* Tutt, 1906.

- [JS] *Thymelicus lineola* f. *diluta* Graves, 1925. Trans. entomol. Soc. Lond. 73(1/2): [43](#).
TL: Shar Deresy (Lebanon).
- [JS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* f.[var.] *hemmingi* Romei, 1927. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 39(9): [127](#).
TL: Sierra Nevada (S Spain).
- [JS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* ssp. *pseudothaumas* Zerny, 1927. Eos 3(3): [342](#).
TL: Losilla (Teruel prov., Spain).
- [JS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* ssp. *melissus* Zerny, 1932. Dt. Entomol. Z. Iris 46(4): 188.
TL: N Lebanon.
- [JS] *Adopaea* [sic] *lineola* f. *forax* Hemming, 1934. Entomologist 67(859): 198.
TL: Palestine.
- [JS] *Adopaea lineola* race *italamixta* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 96, pl. 3, fig. 96-104.
TL: Sesto Fiorentino (Toscana, Italy).
- [SR] *Adopaea lineola* race *clara* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 96-97.
Stat. rev. for *Adopaea lineola* ab. *clara* Tutt, 1906.
- [SR] *Adopaea lineola* race *intermedia* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 98, pl. 4, fig. 8-13.
Stat. nov. for *Adopaea lineola* ab. *intermedia* Tutt, 1906.
- [SR] *Adopaea lineola* race *major* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 98, pl. 4, fig. 14-19.
Stat. nov. for *Adopaea lineola* ab. *major* Tutt, 1906.
- [JS] *Thymelicus lineola* race *ifranensis* Picard, 1948. Bull. Soc. Sci. nat. Maroc 28: [128-129](#).
TL: Ifrane (Maroc).

Subfamily

Pyrginae Burmeister, 1878

- [ORIG] Pyrgidae Burmeister, 1878. Descr. phys. Rép. Argentine 5: [245-246](#).
TG: *Pyrgus* Hübner, [1819].
- [SS] Antigonini Mabile, 1878. Ann. Soc. Entomol. Belg. 21: [28, nota](#).
TG: *Antigonus* Hübner, [1819].
- [JS] Pyrginae Speyer, 1879. Entomol. Ztg. 40: [484](#).
TG: *Pyrgus* Hübner, [1819].

Tribe

Carcharodini Verity, 1940

- [ORIG] Carcharodidi Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 10.
TG: *Carcharodus* Hübner, [1819].

Genus

Spialia Swinhoe, [1912]

- [ORIG] *Spialia* Swinhoe, [1912]. In: Moore, Lepid. ind. 10: [99](#).
TS: *Hesperia galba* Fabricius, 1793 by original designation.

- [JH] *Powellia* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [218](#).
nec Maskell, 1879. Trans. Proc. New Zeal. Inst. 11: [223](#).
TS: *Papilio sao* Hübner, 1800 (= *Papilio sertorius* Hoffmanssegg, 1804) by original designation.
- [RN] *Spialia* sect. *Neospialia* Koçak, 1989. Priamus 5(1/2): [67](#).
Replacement name for *Powellia* Tutt, 1906 nec Maskell, 1879.
TS: *Papilio sertorius* Hoffmanssegg, 1804 by original designation.

Subgenus

Spialia Swinhoe, [1912]

- [ORIG] *Spialia* Swinhoe, [1912]. In: Moore, Lepid. ind. 10: [99](#).
TS: *Hesperia galba* Fabricius, 1793 by original designation.
- [JH] *Powellia* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [218](#).
nec Maskell, 1879. Trans. Proc. New Zeal. Inst. 11: [223](#).
TS: *Papilio sao* Hübner, 1800 (= *Papilio sertorius* Hoffmanssegg, 1804) by original designation.
- [RN] *Spialia* sect. *Neospialia* Koçak, 1989. Priamus 5(1/2): [67](#).
Replacement name for *Powellia* Tutt, 1906 nec Maskell, 1879.
TS: *Papilio sertorius* Hoffmanssegg, 1804 by original designation.

Spialia (Spialia) ali (Oberthür, 1881)

- [ORIG] *Syrichthus ali* Oberthür, 1881. Étud. Entomol. 6: [61](#), [pl. 2](#), [fig. 3](#).
TL: prov. Oran (Algeria).
- [JS] *Syrichthus sao* f. *therapnoides* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. lépid. comp. 4: [385](#), [678](#), [pl. 54](#), [fig. 448](#).
TL: Sebdo (Algeria).

Spialia (Spialia) therapne (Rambur, 1832)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia therapne* Rambur, 1832. Ann. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1: [265](#), [pl. 7](#), [fig. 4](#).
TL: Corsica (S France).
- [IFS] *Spialia hibiscæ* (eserge *therapne*) f. *retrograda* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia. 1: 80, pl. 3, fig. 75-76.
TL: Valle del Gennargentu (Sardinia, Italy).

Spialia (Spialia) sertorius (Hoffman[n]segg, 1804)

- [ORIG] *Papilio sertorius* Hoffman[n]segg, 1804. Mag. Insektenk. 3: [203](#).
TL: Germany.
- [RJ] *Papilio hibiscæ* Hübner, [1793]. Schmett. Lepid. Linn. Eur. Heer: 15.
Papilio hibiscæ Hübner, [1793] was placed on the Official Index of Rejected and invalid specific names in Zoology, Name No 980 by Opinion 975 (ICZN, 1971).
- [JH] *Papilio sao* Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 93](#), [fig. 471-472](#), [1806]: [70](#).
TL: Germany ; nec *Papilio sao* Bergsträsser, 1779. Nomencl. Ins. 2: [67](#), [pl. 40](#), [fig. 8-9](#).
- [JS] *Papilio eucrate* Ochsenheimer, [1808]. Schmett. Eur. 1(2): [213](#).
TL: Portugal.

- [IFS] *Hesperia sao* var.(gen.II.) *aestiva* Melcón, 1910. Bol. R. Soc. Esp. Hist. Nat. 10: [231](#).
TL: Serrania de Cuenca (Spain).
- [IFS] *Powellia sao* gen.II. *gracilis* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [28](#).
TL: Florence (Italy).
- [SR] *Powellia sao* race *gracilis* Verity, 1921. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 33(10): [173-174](#).
TL: Fegana Valley (Tuscany, Italy) ; Stat. rev. for *Powellia sao* gen.II. *gracilis* Verity, 1919 (infrasubspecific).
- [IFS] *Powellia sao* *sao* Gen.II. *parvula* Verity, 1921. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 33(10): [173-174](#).
TL: Atzwang (South Tyrol, NE Italy).
- [JS] *Powellia sao* race *guadarramensis* Warren, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [77](#).
TL: La Granja de San Ildefonso (prov. Segovia, C Spain).
- [JS] *owellia sertorius* race *gavarniensis* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 74(1): [139, pl. 49, fig. 6-8](#).
TL: Gavarnie (dep. Hautes-Pyrénées, S France).
- [JS] *Powellia sao* race *alioides* Verity, 1926. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 38(7/8): [103](#).
TL: Oulx (Piedmont, NW Italy).

Spialia (Spialia) rosae Hernández-Roldán, Dapporto, Dincă, Vicente & Vila, 2016

- [ORIG] *Spialia rosae* Hernández-Roldán, Dapporto, Dincă, Vicente & Vila, 2016. Molecular Ecology 25(17): 4281.
TL: Puerto de la Ragua (Sierra Nevada, prov. Granada, Spain).

Spialia (Spialia) orbifer (Hübner, [1823])

- [ORIG] *Papilio orbifer* Hübner, [1823]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 161, fig. 803-806](#).
TL: - (Hungary).
- [JS] *Hesperia eucrate* var. *tesselloides* Herrich-Schäffer, [1845]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [154, pl.\(Hesp.\) 2, fig. 10-11](#).
TL: Sicily ? (Turkey).
- [JS] *Hesperia orbifer* var. *hilaris* Staudinger, 1901. In: Staudinger & Rebel, Cat. Lepid. pal. Fauneng.: [96](#).
TL: Mardin (SE Turkey).

Subgenus

Platygnathia Picard, [1948]

- [ORIG] *Platygnathia* Picard, [1948]. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 52(8): [132](#).
TS: *Hesperia phlomidis* Herrich-Schäffer, [1845] by original designation.

Spialia (Platygnathia) phlomidis (Herrich-Schäffer, [1845])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia phlomidis* Herrich-Schäffer, [1845]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [153, 164, pl. \(Hesperides\) 2, fig. 8-9](#).
TL: Sea of Marmara (NW Turkey).
- [JS] *Syrichtus jason* Oberthür, 1912. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 6: [75-76, pl. 137, fig. 1211](#).
TL: ? (Turkey).
- [JS] *Syrichtus phlomidis* ssp. *eupator* Hemming, 1932. Entomologist 65: 182.
TL: Amasia (Turkey).

- [JS] *Spialia phlomidis* ssp. *hermona* Evans, 1957. Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (12)9: [750](#).
TL: Mt. Hermon (Syria).
- [JS] *Spialia phlomidis* ssp. *kiki* Higgins, 1974. J. Entomol. (B)43(1): [83-87, fig.](#)
TL: Cedar Mt. (Lebanon).

Spialia (Platygnathia) doris (Walker, 1870)

- [ORIG] *Nisoniades doris* Walker, 1870. Entomologist 5(76): [56-57](#).
TL: Tajora (Bab-el-Mandeb Strait, Djibouti).
- [JS] *Pyrgus evanidus* var. *adenensis* Butler, 1884. Proc. Zool. Soc. London 1884: [493](#).
TL: ? (Turkey).
- [JS] *Hesperia amenophis* Reverdin 1914. Bull. Soc. Lépid. Genève 3: 55, pl. 3, fig. 5-11.
TL: Heliopolis (Egypt).
- [JS] *Spialia doris* ssp. *daphne* Evans, 1949. Cat. Hesp. Eur. Asia Austr.: [177](#).
TL: Ziz Valley (High Atlas, Morocco).

Genus

Favria Tutt, 1906

- [ORIG] *Favria* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Butt. 8: [218](#).
TS: *Hesperia cribrellum* Eversmann, 1841 by original designation.

Favria cribrellum (Eversmann, 1841)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia cribrellum* Eversmann, 1841. Bull. Soc. imp. nat. Mosc. 14(1): [25-27](#).
TL: Orenburg (S Ural, Volga distr., Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Muschampia cribrellum* ssp. *inexpectata* Davkov & Mérit, 2018. Lépidoptères 27(69): [3-7, fig.](#)
TL: Mt. Olympus (Greece).

Genus

Muschampia Tutt, 1906

- [ORIG] *Muschampia* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Butt. 8: [218](#).
TS: *Papilio proto* Esper, 1830 by original designation.

Subgenus

Muschampia Tutt, 1906

- [ORIG] *Muschampia* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Butt. 8: [218](#).
TS: *Papilio proto* Esper, 1830 by original designation.
- [JS] *Tuttia* Warren, 1926. Trans. R. entomol. Soc. Lond. 74: [15](#).
TS: *Papilio tessellum* Hübner, 1800 by original designation.

Muschampia (Muschampia) tessellum (Hübner, [1803])

- [ORIG] *Papilio tessellum* Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 93, fig. 469-470](#), [1806]: [70](#).
TL: Russian Federation.
- [JS] *Papilio mazzola* Ochsenheimer, 1816. Schmett. Eur. 4: [158](#).
TL: Russian Federation.
- [JS] *Papilio hibisci* (Boeber): Ochsenheimer, 1816. Schmett. Eur. 4: [158](#).
TL: Russian Federation.
- [JS] *Hesperia nomas* Lederer, 1855. Verh. Zool.-bot. Ver. Wien 5: [193, pl. 1, fig. 7](#).
TL: Beyrout (Lebanon).
- [JS] *Muschampia tessellum* ssp. *tersa* Evans, 1949. Catal. Hesp. Eur. Asia Austr. Brit. Mus.: [181](#).
TL: Kurdistan (Iraq).

Muschampia (Muschampia) proto (Esper, [1808])

- [ORIG] *Papilio proto* Esper, [1808]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. Suppl. 2: [pl. 123 \(cont. 78\), fig. 5-6](#), [1830]: [32-33](#).
TL: Portugal.
- [JS] *Papilio proto* Ochsenheimer, 1808. Schmett. Eur. 1(2): [210](#).
TL: Portugal.
- [JS] *Hesperia proto* race *aragonensis* Sagarra, 1924. Buttl. Inst. catal. Hist. nat. (2)4(9): [203-204](#).
TL: Albarracín (prov. Teruel, Spain).
- [JS] *Muschampia proto* race *nigrita* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [54-55](#).
TL: Cuenca (prov. Cuenca, Spain).
- [JS] *Muschampia proto* race *fulvosatura* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [55](#).
TL: Sebdou (Algeria).
- [JH] *Muschampia proto* race *gigas* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [55](#).
TL: Azrou (Morocco).
- [NN] *Sloperia proto* race *macroproto* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. entoml. Fr. 1928(8): [141](#).
Nom. nov. pro *Muschampia proto gigas* Verity, 1925 nec *Pyrgus gigas* Bremer, 1864. Mém. Acad. Imp. Sci. St.-Pétersb. (8)8(1): [96, pl. 8, fig. 3](#).
- [JS] *Sloperia proto* f. *williamsi* Querci, 1932. Treb. Mus. Ciènc. Nat. Barc. 14: [248](#).
TL: Portugal.
- [JS] *Muschampia proto evansi* Bryk, 1940. Ark. Zool. 32A(22): 25, pl. 4, fig. 23.
TL: Spain.
- [JS] *Muschampia proto* ssp. *lambesa* Evans, 1949. Catal. Hesp. Eur. Asia Austr. Brit. Mus.: [183](#).
TL: Lambese (NE Algeria).
- [JS] *Muschampia proto* ssp. *chelalae* Gómez Bustillo, 1973. SHILAP Revta. lepid. 1(1-2): [32-33, pl. \[1\], fig. 7](#).
TL: Campo Real (prov. Madrid, C Spain).

Muschampia (Muschampia) proteides (Wagner, 1929)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia proto* ssp. *proteides* Wagner, 1929. Mitt. Münch. Entomol. Ges. 19(1): [Erklärung zu Tafel II, pl. 2, fig. 26](#).
TL: Akşehir (Konya prov., Turkey).

- [JS] *Hesperia proto* ssp. *lycaonius* Wagner, 1929. Mitt. Münch. Entomol. Ges. 19(2-4): [64](#).
TL: Akşehir (Konya prov., Turkey).
- [JS] *Syrichthus hieromax* Hemming, 1932. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 80(2): [291-293, pl. 15, fig. 23, pl. 16, fig. 50](#).
TL: W Ajlun (Jordan).
- [JS] *Sloperia sovietica* Sichel, 1964. Mem. Soc. Entomol. Ital. 43: [166-171, fig.](#)
TL: Sarepta (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Muschampia proteides* ssp. *stepporum* Benyamini & Avni, 2001. Linneana Belg. 18(1): [45-54, fig.](#)
TL: Ma'ale Efraim (Palestine).

Muschampia (Muschampia) alta (Schwingenschuss, 1942)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia proto* ssp. *alta* Schwingenschuss, 1942. Z. Wien. Entomol.-Ver. 27(8): [182](#).
TL: Taormina (Messina prov., Sicily, Italy).

Muschampia (Muschampia) mohammed (Oberthür, 1887)

- [ORIG] *Syrichthus mohammed* Oberthür, 1887. Bull. séances bibliogr. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1887: [xlvi-xlix](#).
TL: Sebdo (Tlemcen prov., Algeria).
- [JS] *Syrichthus ahmed* Oberthür, 1912. Étud. Lépid. Comp. 6: [108, 342, pl. 140, fig. 1259-1260](#).
TL: Lambèse (NE Algeria)
- [JS] *Hesperia caid* Le Cerf, 1923. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 28(15): [198](#).
TL: Oulmès (prov. Khemisset, Morocco).

Muschampia (Muschampia) leuzeae (Oberthür, 1881)

- [ORIG] *Syrichthus leuzeae* Oberthür, 1881. Étud. Entomol. 6: [60, pl. 3, fig. 10](#).
TL: Mascara (Algeria).

Subgenus

Reverdinus Ragusa, [1919]

- [ORIG] *Reverdinus* Ragusa, [1919]. Nat. Sicil. 23(7-12): [172-173](#).
TS: *Papilio altheae* Hübner, 1800 by subsequent designation by Lindsey, 1925. Ann. Entomol. Soc. Am. 18(1): [100](#).
- [JS] *Lavatheria* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 11, 22.
TS: *Papilio lavatherae* Esper, 1783 by original designation.

Muschampia (Reverdinus) floccifera (Zeller, 1847)

- [ORIG] *Hesperia floccifera* Zeller, 1847. Isis von Oken 1847(4): [286-287](#).
TL: Syracuse (Sicily, Italy).
- [RJ] *Papilio alchymillae* Hübner, [1793]. Schmett. Lepid. Linn. Heer: 15.
TL: Hanau (Germany) ; The name *Papilio alchymillae* Hübner, [1790-1793] was placed on the Official Index of Rejected and Invalid Species Names in Zoology by ICZN, 1971 - Opinion 975. Bull. 28(5/6): [154](#) (Name No 979).
- [JH] *Papilio altheae* Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 90, fig. 452-453](#), [1806]: [63](#).
TL: Germany ; *nec*, incorrect spelling for *Papilio althaeae* Esper, [1783]: [149](#) (= *Papilio malvae* Linnaeus, 1759).

- [JS] *Erynnis (Carcharodus) altheae* race *australiformis* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [27](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy).
- [NN] *Carcharodus imperator* Hemming, 1934. Stylops 3: 99.
Nom. nov. pro *Papilio altheae* Hübner, [1803], nec *Papilio althaeae* Esper, [1783].
- [JS] *Spilothyrsus altheae* race *siccior* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(suppl.): [\(5\)](#).
TL: Terme di Valdieri (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Carcharodus floccifera* var. *rungsi* Picard, 1948. Lambillionea 48(3-4): 27.
TL: Gard (S France).
- [JS] *Carcharodus floccifera* race *pyrenaicus* Picard, 1948. Rev. Fr. Lépid. 11(15-16): 325.
TL: Gègre (Hautes-Pyrénées, France).
- [JS] *Reverdinus floccifer* ssp. *habida* Kauffmann, 1955. Mitt. schweiz. Entoml. Ges. 28(3): [288-290, fig. 1-8](#).
TL: Bab el Taza (Morocco).

Muschampia (Reverdinus) orientalis (Reverdin, 1913)

- [ORIG] *Carcharodus orientalis* Reverdin, 1913. Bull. Soc. lépid. Genève 2(1-4): [225, 230-235, pl. 21, fig. 14](#).
TL: Peloponnese (S Greece).
- [JS] *Carcharodus orientalis* var. *centralanatolica* Pfeiffer, 1927. Mitt. Entomol. Ges. Münch. 17(1-6): [44-45](#).
TL: Turkey.
- [IFS] *Spilothyrsus orientalis* gen. II. *postorientalis* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 33(8): [140](#).
TL: Constantinople (= Istanbul, W Turkey).
- [IFS] *Spilothyrsus orientalis* gen. II. *aestatis* Graves, 1928. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 40(5): [77](#).
TL: Constantinople (= Istanbul, W Turkey).
- [JS] *Carcharodus orientalis* ssp. *maccabaeus* Hemming, 1932. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 80(2): [295, pl. 15, fig. 18-19, pl. 16, fig. 45-46](#).
TL: Sukhni, N Zerqa (Jordan).
- [JS] *Carcharodus orientalis* ssp. *teberdinus* Devjatkin, 1990. Entomol. Rev. 69(4): [933-935](#).
TL: Teberda (Karachay–Cherkess Rep., Russian Federation).

Muschampia (Reverdinus) stauderi (Reverdin, 1913)

- [ORIG] *Carcharodus stauderi* Reverdin, 1913. Bull. Soc. lépid. Genève 2(1-4): [225, 230-235, pl. 21, fig. 5, 12](#).
TL: El Kantara, El Kroubs (Algeria).
- [JS] *Carcharodus ramses* Reverdin, 1914. Bull. Soc. lépid. Genève 3: 38, fig.
TL: Maryut (Egypt).
- [JS] *Erynnis barcaeus* Turati, 1927. Atti Soc. Ital. Sci. Nat. 63: [37-41](#), pl. 1, fig. 20-21.
TL: Libya.
- [IFS] *Erynnis stauderi* gen. II *fulvissima* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [43-44](#).
TL: Syria, Turkey.
- [JS] *Erynnis oberthuri* race *ambigua* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [43-44](#).
TL: Syria, Turkey.
- [JS] *Erynnis stauderi* f. *obscurata* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [44](#).
TL: Algeria.

[JS] *Carcharodus stauderi* ssp. *romeii* Rothschild, 1933. Novit. Zool. 38(2): [323](#).
TL: Ketama (Morocco).

Muschampia (Reverdinus) baeticus (Rambur, [1839])

[ORIG] *Syrichtus baeticus* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2(4): [pl. 12, fig. 3-4](#).
TL: Andalusia (S Spain).

[JS] *Pamphila marrubii* Rambur, [1842]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2(6): 323.
TL: Andalusia (S Spain).

[JS] *Carcharodus baeticus* race *octodurensis* Oberthür, 1911. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 5(1): [195](#).
TL: Martigny (Valais, Switzerland).

[JS] *Erynnis (Carcharodus) boeticus* [sic] race *rostagnoi* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [27](#).
TL: Oricola, Latium (prov. L'Aquila, C Italy).

[JS] *Erynnis (Carcharodus) boeticus* [sic] race *oberthueri* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [27](#).
TL: Sicily (S Italy).

[JS] *Erynnis marrubii* race *fulvescens* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [42-43](#).
TL: Rognac (dep. Bouches-du-Rhône, S France).

[IFS] *Erynnis marrubii fulvescens* gen. I *grisea* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [42-43](#).
TL: Rognac (dep. Bouches-du-Rhône, S France).

[IFS] *Erynnis marrubii fulvescens* gen. III *aegra* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [42-43](#).
TL: Rognac (dep. Bouches-du-Rhône, S France).

[IFS] *Erynnis marrubii fulvescens* f. *viridescens* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [43](#).
TL: dep. Bouches-du-Rhône ? (S France).

[JS] *Erynnis marrubii* race *fulva* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [43](#).
TL: Cuenca (C Spain).

[JS] *Spilothyris marrubii* race *fonti* Sagarra, 1930. Butll. Catal. Hist. Nat. (2)10(7): [118](#).
TL: Horcajo, Sierra Nevada (S Spain).

Muschampia (Reverdinus) lavatherae (Esper, [1783])

[ORIG] *Papilio lavatherae* Esper, [1783]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(2): [148-149](#), [pl. 82 \(cont. 32\)](#), [fig. 4](#).
TL: France ; Switzerland.

[JH] *Papilio tages* Sulzer, 1776. Gesch. Ins. 1: [146](#), 2: [pl. 19, fig. 6-7](#).
nec Papilio tages Linnaeus, 1758: [485](#).

[JS] *Carcharodus lavatherae* var. *rufescens* Oberthür, 1914. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 10: [407-408](#), [pl. 296, fig. 4433](#).
TL: Sebdou, Méchéria (Algeria).

[JS] *Carcharodus lavatherae* ssp. *internirufus* Rothschild, 1914. Novit. Zool. 21(4): [311](#).
TL: Ain Sefra, Guelt-es-Stel (C Algeria).

[JS] *Carcharodus tauricus* Reverdin, 1915. Bull. Soc. Lépid. Genève 3(2): 103-108, pl. 5, fig. 1-2.
TL: Külek (Turkey).

[JS] *Erynnis (Carcharodus) lavatherae* race *australior* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [27](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy).

- [JS] *Erynnis lavatherae* race *australissima* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(3): [41-42](#).
TL: Sebdou (Algeria).
- [JS] *Carcharodus lavatherae* f. *chlorotes* Dannehl, 1925. Entomol. Z. 39(20): [82](#).
TL: Terlan (South Tyrol prov., NE Italy).
- [JS] *Carcharodus lavatherae* race *nigroboscuroata* Verity, 1938. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 50(suppl.): [1-3](#).
TL: Skala (N Greece).
- [JS] *Carcharodus lavatherae* var. *rungsi* Picard, 1948. Lambillionea 48(3-4): 28.
TL: Gard (S France).

Genus

Carcharodus Hübner, [1819]

- [ORIG] *Carcharodus* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett. (7): [110](#).
TS: *Papilio alceae* Esper, [1780] by designation by Opinion 181 (ICZN, 1946: [607](#)) and by Opinion 270 (ICZN, 1954: [29](#)).
- [JS] *Spilolhyrus* Duponchel, [1835]. Hist. Nat. Lépid. suppl. 1: <http://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/37742#page/523/mode/1up>.
TS: *Papilio alceae* Esper, [1780] by designation by Opinion 270 (ICZN, 1954: [29](#)).
- [IS] *Spilolhyrus* Duponchel, [1835]. Hist. Nat. Lépid. suppl. 1: [419](#).
Incorrect spelling for *Spilolhyrus* Duponchel, [1835].

Carcharodus alceae (Esper, [1780])

- [ORIG] *Papilio alceae* Esper, [1780]. Schmett. Abb. Nat.1(2): [4-6](#), [pl. 51](#), [fig. 3](#).
TL: Germany.
- [ND] *Papilio fritillarius* Poda, 1761 Ins. Mus. Graec.: [79](#).
TL: Graz (Austria) ; Nomen dubium.
- [JH] *Hapilio maluae* [sic] Bergsträsser, 1780. Nomencl. Ins. 4: [39-40](#), [pl. 91](#), [fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Germany ; *nec Papilio malvae* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [485](#).
- [JS] *Papilio malvarum* Hoffman[n]segg, 1804. Mag. Insektenk. 3: [198](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Hesperia malvarum* var. *nostras* Zeller, 1847. Isis von Oken 1847(4): [285-286](#).
TL: Sicily (S Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia malvarum* var. *australis* Zeller, 1847. Isis von Oken 1847(4): [285-286](#).
TL: Sicily (S Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia gemina* Lederer, 1853. Verh. Zool.-bot. Ver. Wien 2: [26](#), [50](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Spilolhyrus alceae* var. *aestiva* Hormuzaki, 1897. Verh. Zool.-bot. Ver. Wien 47: [164](#).
TL: Bukowina (Romania ; Ukraine).
- [JS] *Erynnis alceae* f. *fulvocarens* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [54](#).
TL: Tenna Valley, Sibillini Mts. (C Italy).
- [IFS] *Erynnis alceae* race *magnaustralis* Verity, 1926. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 36(7-8): [106](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy).

- [JS] *Carcharodus fritillarius* race *claraustralis* Verity, 1937. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 49(suppl.): [2](#).
TL: Mount Carmel (Israel).
- [JS] *Carcharodus fritillarius* race *claraminima* Verity, 1937. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 49(suppl.): [2](#).
TL: Malatia (Turkey).
- [JS] *Carcharodus alceae* f. *exigua* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurn. It. 1: 14.
TL: Atina (Lazio, C Italy).
- [JS] *Carcharodus alceae* var. *corsicus* Picard, 1948. Rev. Fr. Lépid. 11(15-16): 324.
TL: Corse (S France).

Carcharodus tripolina (Verity, 1925)

- [ORIG] *Erynnis alceae* race *tripolina* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [54](#).
TL: Garian plateau, S Tripoli (Libya).

Tribe

Erynnini Brues & Melander, 1932

- [ORIG] Erynninae Brues & Melander, 1932. Bull. Mus. comp. Zool. 73: [235-236](#).
TG: *Erynnis* Schrank, 1801.

Genus

Erynnis Schrank, 1801

- [ORIG] *Erynnis* Schrank, 1801. Fauna Boica 2(1): [152](#), [157-160](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Scudder, 1872. 4th Ann. Rep. Peabody Acad. Sci. (1871): [70-71](#).
- [JS] *Thymele* Fabricius, 1807. In Illiger, *Mag. Insektenk.* 6: [287](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Westwood, 1839. Introd. Mod. Classif. Ins. 2(Synopsis): [88](#).
- [JS] *Thymele* [Illiger], 1807. *Allg.-Lit. Ztg. Halle* 1807(2)(303): [1180](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Westwood, 1839. Introd. Mod. Classif. Ins. 2(Synopsis): [88](#).
- [JS] *Astycus* Hübner, 1822. *Syst.-alph. Verz.*: [1](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Hemming, 1933. Entomologist 66(844): 200.
- [JS] *Thanaos* Boisduval, [1834]. *Icon. Hist. Lépid. Europ.* 1(23): [240](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Blanchard, 1840. Hist. Nat. Ins. 3: [469](#).

Subgenus

Erynnis Schrank, 1801]

- [ORIG] *Erynnis* Schrank, 1801. Fauna Boica 2(1): [152](#), [157-160](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Scudder, 1872. 4th Ann. Rep. Peabody Acad. Sci. (1871): [70-71](#).
- [JS] *Thymele* Fabricius, 1807. In Illiger, *Mag. Insektenk.* 6: [287](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Westwood, 1839. Introd. Mod. Classif. Ins. 2(Synopsis): [88](#).
- [JS] *Thymele* [Illiger], 1807. *Allg.-Lit. Ztg. Halle* 1807(2)(303): [1180](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Westwood, 1839. Introd. Mod. Classif. Ins. 2(Synopsis): [88](#).

- [JS] *Astycus* Hübner, 1822. Syst.-alph. Verz.: [1](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Hemming, 1933. Entomologist 66(844): 200.
- [JS] *Thanaos* Boisduval, [1834]. *Icon. Hist. Lépid. Europ.* 1(23): [240](#).
TS: *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Blanchard, 1840. Hist. Nat. Ins. 3: [469](#).

Erynnis (Erynnis) tages (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio tages* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [485](#).
TL: Sweden..
- [JS] *Papilio morio* Scopoli, 1763. Entomol. Carn.: [181-182](#).
TL: Krain (Slovenia).
- [JS] *Papilio geryon* Rottemburg, 1775. Naturforscher 6: [31-32](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Thanaos cervantes* Graslin, 1836. Ann. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 5: [558-561](#), [pl. 17 B.](#), [fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Sierra Nevada (S Spain).
- [JH] *Hesperia cervantes* Freyer, [1842]. Neuere Beitr. Schmett. 5(67): [56-57](#), [pl. 417](#), [fig. 3](#).
nec Graslin, 1836..
- [JS] *Hesperia unicolor* Freyer, [1847]. Neuere Beitr. Schmett. 6(85): [37](#), [pl. 505 fig. 1](#).
TL: Islands in Greece.
- [IFS] *Nisoniades tages* ab. *clarus* Caradja, 1895. Dt. Entomol. Z. 8: [61](#).
TL: Grumăzești (Romania).
- [JS] *Nisoniades tages* race *subclarus* Verity, 1921. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 33(10): [172](#).
TL: Campodazzo, Merano (prov. South Tyrol, NE Italy).
- [JS] *Erynnis tages* race *magnatages* Verity, 1938. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 50(suppl.): [1](#).
TL: Skala (N Greece).
- [SR] *Erynnis tages* race *clarus* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurn. It. 1: 8-9.
Statut rev. for *Nisoniades tages* ab. *clarus* Caradja, 1895.
- [JS] *Erynnis tages* race *brunnea* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurn. It. 1: 9.
TL: Torre Pellice (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Erynnis tages* ssp. *baynesi* Higgins, 1956. Entomologist 89: 241-242.
TL: The Burren (Ireland).

Subgenus

Hesperopegasus Seven, 2002

- [ORIG] *Hesperopegasus* Seven, 2002. In: Koçak & Kemal, Misc. Pap. CESA 82/85: 27, fig.
TS: *Thanaos marloyi* Boisduval, [1834] by original designation.
- [JS] *Hallia* Tutt, 1906. *Nat. Hist. Brit. Butts.* 1(8/9): [261](#).
TS: *Thanaos marloyi* Boisduval, [1834] by original designation ; *nec* Edwards & Haime, 1850. Brit. Foss. Corals (Pal. Soc. 3): lxvi.

Erynnis (Hesperopegasmus) marloyi (Boisduval, [1834])

[ORIG] *Thanaos marloyi* Boisduval, [1834]. Icon. Hist. Lépid. 1: [241](#), [pl. 47](#), [fig. 6-7](#).

TL: Peloponnese (S Greece).

[JS] *Hesperia sericea* Freyer, [1839]. Neuere Beitr. Schmett. 3(45): [102](#), [pl. 265](#), [fig. 4](#).

TL: Constantinople (Turkey).

Tribe

Pyrgini Burmeister, 1878

[ORIG] Pyrgidae Burmeister, 1878. Descr. phys. Rép. Argentine 5: [245-246](#).

TG: *Pyrgus* Hübner, [1819].

Genus

Pyrgus Hübner, [1819]

[ORIG] *Pyrgus* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [109](#).

TS: *Papilio alveolus* Hübner, 1800 (= *P. malvae* Linnaeus, 1758) by designation by Westwood, 1841. Brit. Butterflies Transf.: [120](#).

[JS] *Urbanus* Hübner, [1806]. Tentamen: [\[1\]](#).

TS: *Papilio malvae* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.

[JS] *Syrichtus* Boisduval, [1834]. Icon. Hist. Lépid. 1: 230-232.

TS: *Papilio malvae* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Blanchard, 1845. Hist. Nat. Ins. 2: [347-348](#).

Subgenus

Pyrgus Hübner, [1819]

[ORIG] *Pyrgus* Hübner, [1819]. Verz. bekannt. Schmett.: [109](#).

TS: *Papilio alveolus* Hübner, 1800 (= *P. malvae* Linnaeus, 1758) by designation by Westwood, 1841. Brit. Butterflies Transf.: [120](#).

[JS] *Urbanus* Hübner, [1806]. Tentamen: [\[1\]](#).

TS: *Papilio malvae* Linnaeus, 1758 by monotypy.

[JS] *Hesperia (Hemiteleomorpha)* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. Lond. 74(1): 19, 72.

TS: *Papilio malvae* Linnaeus, 1758 by designation by Hemming, 1934. Stylops 3(6): [143](#).

Pyrgus (Pyrgus) malvoides (Elwes & Edwards, 1897)

[ORIG] *Hesperia malvoides* Elwes & Edwards, 1897. Trans. Zool. Soc. Lond. 14(4): [156](#), [160](#), [pl. 23](#), [fig. 27-27a](#).

TL: Biarritz (SW France).

[JS] *Hesperia malvae* race [ab.?] *australis* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [224](#).

TL: Draguignan (S France).

[JS] *Hesperia malvae* race *pyrenaica* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [225](#).

TL: Vernet-les-Bains (S France).

[JS] *Hesperia malvae* race *andalusica* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [225-226](#).

TL: Canales de la Sierra (Spain).

[JS] *Hesperia malvae* race *alpina* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [226](#).

TL: Cogne (Aosta, NW Italy) ; *nec* Erschoff, 1874. Fedsch. Lepid. Turkestan : 24.

- [JS] *Syrichthus malvae* f. *fritillans* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Léop. comp. 4: [393-394](#), [679](#), [pl. 54, fig. 461-463](#).
TL: Vernet-les-Bains (S France).
- [JS] *Hesperia malvoides* race *tutti* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [28](#).
TL: Locarno (Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia (Hemiteleomorpha) malvoides* race *modestior* Verity, 1929. Trab. Mus. Cienc. Nat. Barc. 11(4): [6-7](#).
TL: Italy.
- [JS] *Hesperia (Hemiteleomorpha) malvoides* f. *melotiformis* Verity, 1929. Trab. Mus. Cienc. Nat. Barc. 11(4): [6-7](#).
TL: TL: Pian di Mugnone, Florence (Italy).
- [JS] *Pyrgus malvoides* race? *alpestris* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 42.
Replacement name, nom. nov. for *Hesperia malvae alpina* Tutt, 1906 nec Erschoff, 1874.

Pyrgus (Pyrgus) malvae (Linnaeus, 1758)

- [ORIG] *Papilio malvae* Linnaeus, 1758. Syst. Nat. (ed. 10)1: [485](#).
TL: Trosa (Sweden).
- [JS] *Papilio malvae minor* Esper, [1777]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(1): [pl. 36, fig. 5](#), [1779]: [345-346](#).
TL: -.
- [JS] *Papilio sao* Bergsträsser, 1779. Nom. Ins. 2: [67](#), pl. 40, fig. 8-9.
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Papilio taras* Bergsträsser, 1780. Nom. Ins. 4: [40](#), [pl. 91, fig. 5-6](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Papilio althaeae* Esper, [1783]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(2): [149](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Papilio fritillum* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Ins. 2: [91](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JH] *Papilio lavaterae* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Ins. 2: [91](#).
TL: Germany ; nec *Papilio lavatherae* Esper, [1783].
- [JH] *Papilio fritillum* Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 92, fig. 464-465](#), [1806]: [70](#).
TL: Germany ; nec *Papilio fritillum* Fabricius, 1787.
- [JS] *Papilio aveolus* Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 92, fig. 466-467](#).
TL: -.
- [JS] [*Papilio*] *malvarum* Hoffman[n]segg, 1804. Mag. Insektenk. 3: [198](#).
TL: -.
- [JS] *Hesperia cardui* Godart, [1824]. Encycl. Méth. Entomol. 9(2): [784-785](#).
TL: N Germany ; Lappland.
- [JS] *Syrichthus (Hesperia) malvae* race *elegantior* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(suppl.): [6](#).
TL: Rhone Valley (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Pyrgus malvae* ssp. *lucarius* Kauffmann, 1951. Mitt. Schw. Entomol. Ges. 24(4): [345-346](#).
TL: Lopperberg (C Switzerland).

Pyrgus (Pyrgus) melotis (Duponchel, [1834])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia melotis* Duponchel, [1834]. In: Godart, Hist. nat. Lépid. suppl. 1: [257-258](#), [pl. 42](#), [fig. 1-2](#).
TL: Isle of Milos, Greece (see Notes (1): error ?).
- [JS] *Hesperia hypoleucos* Lederer, 1855. Verh. zool.-bot. Ver. Wien 5: [193](#), [pl. 1](#), [fig. 8](#).
TL: Lebanon.
- [JS] *Syrichthus malvae* f. *graecus* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. Lépid. comp. 4: [394](#), [679](#), [pl. 54](#), [fig. 468-469](#).
TL: Greece (see Notes (2): error ?).
- [JS] *Scelotrix melotis* ssp. *jordana* Hemming, 1932. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 80(2): [290](#), [pl. 15](#), [fig. 24-25](#), [pl. 16](#), [fig. 51-52](#).
TL: El Hammie (Jordan), Safed (Israël).
- [JS] *Hesperia pontica* Reverdin, 1914. Bull. Soc. Lépid. Genève 3(1): [66-72](#), [pl. 3](#), [fig. 6, 12](#), [pl. 4](#), [fig. 2-3](#).
TL: Amasya (Turkey).
- [JS] *Hesperia melotis* ssp. *caucasica* Rjabov, 1926. Bull. Sci. Inst. Explor. Reg. Caucase Nord 1: [298](#).
TL: Dzheyrakh (Rep. Ingushetia, Russian Federation).

Subgenus

Scelotrix Rambur, 1858

- [ORIG] *Scelotrix* Rambur, 1858. Cat. syst. lépid. Andal.: [63-65](#).
TS: *Papilio carthami* Hübner, 1813 by designation by Watson, 1893. Proc. Zool. Soc. Lond. 1893: [64](#).
- [JS] *Hesperia* (*Teleomorpha*) Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. Lond. 74(1): 18, 72.
TS: *Papilio carthami* Hübner, [1813] by designation by Hemming, 1934. Stylops 3(6): [143](#).

Pyrgus (Scelotrix) carthami (Hübner, [1813])

- [ORIG] *Papilio carthami* Hübner, [1813]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 143](#), [fig. 720-723](#).
TL: S Germany.
- [ND] *Papilio fritillarius* Poda, 1761. Ins. Mus. Graec.: [79](#).
TL: Austria ; nomen dubium (see de Jong, 1987. Zool. Meded. 61(26) : [371-385](#)).
- [RJ] *Papilio maluae* [sic] *maior* Fabricius, 1787. Mantissa Insect. 2: [91](#).
TL: S Russian Federation ; rejected name by Opinion 1599 (ICZN, 1990: [160](#)).
- [JS] *Hesperia moeschleri* Herrich-Schäffer, [1854]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [175](#), [pl. \(Hesperides\) 7](#), [fig. 37-38](#).
TL: Sarepta (= Volgograd, Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Scelotrix galactites* Rambur, 1858. Cat. syst. lépid. Andal.: [68](#).
TL: Andalusia (S Spain).
- [JS] *Scelothrix* [sic] *carthami* var. *valesiaca* Mabille, 1875. Ann. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 5(Bull.): [ccxiv](#).
TL: Switzerland.
- [JS] *Hesperia carthami* var. *major* Mabille, 1904. Gen. Ins. 17: [82](#).
TL: Valais (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Hesperia carthami* var. *rühli* Mabille, 1904. Gen. Ins. 17: [82](#).
TL: -.
- [JS] *Syrichthus carthami* var. *nevadensis* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. lépid. comp. 4: [383-384](#), [pl. 55](#), [fig. 474](#).
TL: Lanjaron, Sierra Nevada (S Spain).

- [JS] *Hesperia carthami* race *speciosa* Verity, 1921. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 33(10): [172-173](#).
TL: Isarco Valley (= Eisacktal, prov. South Tyrol, NE Italy)
- [JH] *Hesperia carthami* ssp. *pyrenaica* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 74: [69, pl. 23, fig. 9-10](#).
TL: Gavarnie (dep. Hautes-Pyrénées, France) ; nec *Hesperia malvae pyrenaica* Tutt, 1906. Nat. Hist. Brit. Lepid. 8: [225](#).
- [JS] *Hesperia carthami* f. *albana* Heinrich, 1928. Dt. Entomol. Z. 1928(3): [187](#).
TL: NW Spain.
- [JS] *Hesperia carthami* race *lucasi* Reverdin, 1929. Bull. Soc. lép. Genève 6(2): [91-92, pl. 2, fig. 5-6](#).
TL: Forêt de Benon (dep. Charente inférieure, France).
- [NN] *Hesperia carthami* race *microcarthami* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 8: 140.
Replacement name, nom. nov. for *Hesperia carthami pyrenaica* Warren, 1926 ; nec *Hesperia malvae pyrenaica* Tutt, 1906.
- [JS] *Hesperia carthami* ssp. *septentrionalis* Alberti, 1938. Stett. Entomol. Ztg. 99(2): [236-238](#).
TL: Bärwalde, Neumark (Germany).
- [JS] *Hesperia carthami* ssp. *analoga* Alberti, 1938. Stett. Entomol. Ztg. 99(2): [244](#).
TL: Trebević, Sarajevo (Bosnia and Herzegovina).
- [JS] *Pyrgus fritillarius* race *nemausensis* Picard, 1948. Lambillionea 48(3-4): 28-29.
TL: Champ de tir de Nîmes (dep. Gard, S France).

Pyrgus (Scelotrix) sidae (Esper, [1784])

- [ORIG] *Papilio sidae* Esper, [1784]. Schmett. Abb. Nat. 1(2): [178-179, pl. 90 \(cont. 40\), fig. 3](#).
TL: Volga region (Russian Federation).
- [JH] *Hesperia onopordi* Herrich-Schäffer, [1848]. Syst. Bearb. Schmett. Eur. 1: [pl. \(Hesperides\) 6, fig. 31-32](#).
TL: -. ; nec *Hesperia onopordi* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 13, p.](#)
- [JH] *Hesperia sidae* race *occidentalis* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [27](#).
TL: W Europe ; nec *Hesperia serratulae occidentalis* Lucas, 1910. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 1910: [62](#).
- [JS] *Hesperia sidae* race *occidua* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [76](#).
TL: Tuscany (Italy).
- [JS] *Pyrgus sidae* ssp. *gargantoi* Martínez & Sánchez, 1987. Shilap 15(60): 371-375.
TL: Hervás (prov. Cáceres, Extremadura, Spain).

Pyrgus (Scelotrix) centaureae (Rambur, [1839])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia centaureae* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 10](#), [1840]: 315-316 (nota).
TL: Tornio and Dalarna (Sweden) or Abisko in Torne Lappmark (N Sweden) (see Opheim, 1959. Astarte 18: [2](#)).
- [JS] *Pyrgus centaureae* ssp. *schöyeni* Opheim, 1959. Astarte 18: [4, fig. 1](#).
TL: Odalen (S Norway).
- [JS] *Pyrgus centaureae lineolata* Kauffmann, 1950. Entomol. Z. 59(23): [177-180, fig.](#)
TL: 'Halbinsel Rybatschi an der Murmanküste' (?? Russian Federation).

Pyrgus (Scelotrix) cacaliae (Rambur, [1839])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia cacaliae* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 6-7, k](#), [1840]: 313-314 (nota).
TL: Alps (SE France).

- [JS] *Hesperia cacaliae cantoniera* Belling, 1926. Int. Entomol. Z. 20: 198.
TL: St. Gotthardo, Ticino Alps (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Pyrgus cacaliae* race *prosensis* Kauffmann, 1946. Boll. Soc. Ticin. Sci. Nat. 41: [75-81, fig. 1-3](#).
TL: St. Gotthardo, Ticino Alps (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Pyrgus (Scelotrix) cacaliae* race *pyrenaeus* Picard, 1947. Rev. fr. Lépid. 11(4): 94-95.
TL: Masivul Bucegi, above Sinaia, jud. Prahova (Romania).
- [JS] *Pyrgus cacaliae* ssp. *hebsgaardii* Bjerregård & Mølgaard, 2023. Phegea 51(1): [42-46, fig.](#)
TL: Masivul Bucegi, above Sinaia, jud. Prahova (Romania).

Pyrgus (Scelotrix) andromedae (Wallengren, 1853)

- [ORIG] *Syrichthus andromedae* Wallengren, 1853. Öfversigt Kongl. Vetenskaps-akad. förhandl. 10(2): [25](#).
TL: Dovre (Norway).
- [JS] *Syrichthus andromedae* var. *borealis* Stichel, 1908. Berl. Entomol. Z. 20: [198](#).
TL: Tysfjorden (N Norway).

Subgenus

Ateleomorpha Warren, 1926

- [ORIG] *Hesperia (Ateleomorpha)* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. Lond. 74(1): 19, 87.
TS: *Hesperia onopordi* Rambur, [1839] by designation by Hemming, 1934. Stylops 3(6): [143](#).

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) serratulae (Rambur, [1839])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia serratulae* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. And. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 9, m](#), [1840]: 318-319.
TL: Spain.
- [JS] *Hesperia caecus* Freyer, [1847]. Neuere Beitr. Schmett. 6(83): [22, pl. 493, fig. 3-4](#).
TL: Tyrol (Austria).
- [JS] *Syrichthus serratulae* var. *major* Staudinger, 1878. Horae Soc. Entomol. Ross. 14: [292](#).
TL: Kerasdere, Taurus (Turkey).
- [JH] *Syrichthus serratulae minor* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Emtomol. Comp. 4: [401, 680, pl. 55, fig. 482](#).
TL: Cauterets (dep. Hautes-Pyrénées, France) ; nec *Papilio malvae minor* Esper, [1777]. Schmett. Abb. Nat.1(1): [pl. 36, fig. 5](#).
- [JH] *Hesperia serratulae* var. *occidentalis* Lucas, 1910. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 1910: [62](#).
TL: Fontenay-le-Comte (dep. Vendée, W France) ; nec *Pyrgus occidentalis* Skinner, 1906. Entomol. News 17(3): [96](#).
- [JS] *Hesperia serratulae* var. *planorum* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [56-57](#).
TL: Friedland (Mecklenburg-Vorpommern, NE Germany).
- [JS] *Hesperia serratulae* var. *fragilis* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [56-57](#).
TL: Vienna (Austria).
- [JH] *Hesperia serratulae* f. *latealbata* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [56-57](#).
TL: Schynige Platte (Bern, C Switzerland).
- [JS] *Hesperia serratulae* ssp. *balcanica* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 74(1): 97-98, pl. 29, fig. 7-12.
TL: Cetinje (Montenegro).

- [JS] *Hesperia serratulae* ssp. *uralensis* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 74(1): 98-99, pl. 29, fig. 1-6.
TL: Uralsk (Kazakhstan).
- [NN] *Hesperia serratulae magnagallica* Verity, 1931. Bull. Soc. Entomol. Fr. 36(13): [201](#).
Replacement name for *Hesperia serratulae* var. *occidentalis* Lucas, 1910 nec *Pyrgus occidentalis* Skinner, 1906.
- [JS] *Hesperia serratulae* var. *clarissima* Heinrich, 1938. Dt. Entomol. Z. 'Iris' 52: 15, fig.
TL: Digne (SE France).
- [JS] *Pyrgus serratulae* race *infraobscurata* Verity, 1938. Entomol. Rec. J. Var 50(suppl.): [3](#).
TL: Skala, S. Dionisio (Greece).
- [JS] *Pyrgus serratulae* race *arvernensis* Picard, 1948. Lambillionea 48(5-6): 35.
TL: France.
- [JS] *Hesperia (Pyrgus) serratulae* ssp. *grisescens* Alberti, 1969. Faun. Abhandl. Staatl. Mus. Tierk. Dresden 2(20): [141-142, fig. 3](#).
TL: Teberda (Karachay-Cherkessia, Russian Federation).

***Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) armoricanus* (Oberthür, 1910)**

- [ORIG] *Syrichthus alveus* f. *armoricanus* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. comp. 4: [411-413](#), [681](#), pl. 57, fig. 509-517.
TL: Rennes (C France).
- [JS] *Hesperia persica* Reverdin, 1913. Bull. Soc. Lépid. Genève 2(4): 218-224, pl. 21, fig. 4, pl. 22, fig. 9.
TL: Kuldsar (Iran).
- [IFS] *Hesperia armoricanus* gen.II *fulvoinspersa* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [27](#).
TL: -.
- [JH] *Syrichthus armoricanus* var. *corsicus* Oberthür, 1919. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1919(7): [130](#).
TL: Corsica (S France).
- [JS] *Hesperia armoricanus* race *rufosatura* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [73](#).
TL: Fontebuona di Vaglia (Tuscany, Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia armoricanus petheri* Romei, 1927. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 39(9): [127](#).
TL: Cuenca (C Spain).
- [JS] *Hesperia persica* var. *prostanae* Pfeiffer, 1927. Mitt. Münch. Entomol. Ges. 17: [45-46](#).
TL: inner Anatolia (Turkey).
- [JS] *Hesperia (Ateleomorpha) armoricanus* f. *cacaotica* Verity, 1929. Trab. Mus. Cienc. Nat. Barc. 11(4): [15](#).
TL: Valle umida del Camaione (prov. Lucca, Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia armoricanus philonides* Hemming, 1931. Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (10)8: 534-535.
TL: Khan Ghaffa (Lebanon).
- [JS] *Hesperia armoricanus* ssp. *disjuncta* Alberti, 1940. Mitt. Münch. Entomol. Ges. 30(1): [252-253](#), pl. 2, fig. 7a.
TL: Halle (Germany).
- [SN] *Pyrgus armoricanus* race *fulvoinspersa* Verity, 1940. Farfalle diurne Italia 1: 70, pl. 3, fig. 14-31.
TL: Valle del Camaione (Lucca), Monte Conca (Firenze) (Italy) ; Stat. nov. for *Hesperia armoricanus* gen.II *fulvoinspersa* Verity, 1919.
- [JS] *Pyrgus armoricanus maroccanus* Picard, 1950. Bull. Soc. Sci. Nat. Maroc 28: [121-122](#).
TL: Ifrane (Maroc).

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) alveus (Hübner, [1803])

- [ORIG] *Papilio alveus* Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 92, fig. 461-463](#), [1806]: [70](#).
TL: Germany.
- [JS] *Pyrgus alveus-fritillum* var. *funginus* Schilde, 1886. Berl. Entomol. Z. 30: [39-49](#).
TL: Vintschgau (prov. South Tyrol, NE Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* var. *scandinavicus* Strand, 1903. Arch. Math. Naturvid. 25: [6-8](#).
TL: Dovre (Norway).
- [JH] *Syrichthus alveus* race *ryffelensis* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. Lépid. comp. 4: [405-408](#), [679](#), [pl. 54, fig. 470-471](#).
TL: Zermatt, Ryffelalp (Valais, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Syrichthus alveus* race *ballotae* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. Lépid. comp. 4: [404](#), [680](#), [pl. 56, fig. 494-495](#).
TL: Dovre (Norway).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* var. *alticola* Rebel, 1910. In: Berge's, Schmetterlingsbuch (ed. 9): [84](#).
TL: Stilsferjoch, Stelvio Pass (N Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* race *centralitaliae* Verity, 1920. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 32(1): [4](#).
TL: Piceno, Sibillini Mts. (C Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* race *accreta* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [55](#).
TL: Simplon, ... (Switzerland).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* race *grandis* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [55](#).
TL: Saint-Martin-Vésubie (dep. Alpes-Maritimes, SE France).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* f. *centralhispaniae* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [56](#).
TL: Albarracin (prov. Teruel, Spain).
- [JS] *Hesperia ryffelensis* race *albans* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [56](#).
TL: Olmütz, Moravia (=Olomouc, Czech Republic).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* race *trebevicensis* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 74: [121](#).
TL: Trebević (Bosnia and Herzegovina).
- [JS] *Hesperia alveus* race *jurassica* Warren, 1926. Trans. Entomol. Soc. London 74: [121-122](#), [pl. 42, fig. 9-12](#).
TL: Grand Salève (Jura, E France).
- [JS] *Hesperia (Ateleomorpha) alveus* race *pyrenealpium* Verity, 1929. Trab. Mus. Cienc. Nat. Barc. 11(4): [11](#).
TL: Gèdre (dep. Hautes-Pyrénées, S France).
- [JS] *Hesperia (Ateleomorpha) alveus* race *necaccreta* Verity, 1929. Trab. Mus. Cienc. Nat. Barc. 11(4): [12](#).
TL: Vall de Núria (prov. Girona, NE Spain).
- [JS] *Hesperia (Ateleomorpha) alveus* race *magnalveus* Verity, 1929. Trab. Mus. Cienc. Nat. Barc. 11(4): [12](#).
TL: Oulx (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia (Ateleomorpha) alveus* race *insigniamiscens* Verity, 1929. Trab. Mus. Cienc. Nat. Barc. 11(4): [13-14](#).
TL: Font Quer, Horeajo, Sierra Nevada (S Spain).
- [JH] *Syrichthus alveus* race *claralveus* Verity, 1934. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 46(suppl.): [10-11](#).
TL: Cesana (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JH] *Hesperia alveus* f. *caucasius* Picard, 1949. Rev. Fr. Lépid. 12: 57.
TL: Monts Adjara, Kuban (South Caucasus).

- [JS] *Pyrgus alveus* ssp. *prabornius* Kauffmann, 1951. Mitt. Schw. Entomol. Ges. 24(4): [357-358](#).
TS: Saas Fee, Zermatt (Valais, Switzerland).
- [JS] *Pyrgus reverdini* ssp. *scotti* Warren, 1952. Entomologist 85: 39-41.
TL: Sylkynjärvi, Savonlinna (Finland).
- [JH] *Pyrgus (A.) illensis* ssp. *colurnus* Kauffmann, 1954. Redia 39: 261-274, pl. 2, fig.
TL: Rhaetian Alps, Piedmont, Alto Adige, Lombardy (N Italy).
- [JS] *Pyrgus trebevicensis* ssp. *germanica* Renner, 1983. Caroleinea 41: [133](#).
TL: Schwäbische Alb, Schmiechtal, Hütten (S Germany).
- [ND] *Pyrgus alveus* ssp. *confusa* Renner, 1983. Caroleinea 41: [133-134](#).
TL: ? Alpes ; Nomen nudum.

***Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) warrenensis* (Verity, 1928)**

- [ORIG] *Hesperia alveus* race *warrenensis* Verity, 1928. Bull. Soc. entomol. Fr. 1928(8): [140-141](#).
TL: Lenzerheide (Grisons, Switzerland).
- [JH] *Pyrgus warrenensis* ssp. *occidentalis* Renner, 1991. Neue Entomol. Nachr. 28: [94, pl. 8, fig. 36, pl. 27, fig. 190-193](#).
TL: Grossglockner (Carinthia, Austria) ; nec *Pyrgus occidentalis* Skinner, 1906. Entomol. News 17(3): [96](#).
- [JS] *Pyrgus warrenensis dejongensis* Taymans C., 1992. Bull. Cercle Lépid. Belg./Bull. Belg. Lepid. Kring 21(6): [126-127](#).
TL: Larche (Basses-Alpes, SE France).

***Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) bellieri* (Oberthür, 1910)**

- [ORIG] *Syrichthus alveus* var. *bellieri* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. Lépid. comp. 4: [404-406, 680, pl. 56, fig. 490-491](#).
TL: Larche (dep. Alpes-de-Haute-Provence, SE France).
- [JH] *Hesperia carthami* Duponchel, 1832. In: Godart, Hist. nat. Lépid. suppl. 1: [pl. 42, fig. 3-4](#).
TL: Provence (S France) ; nec Hübner, [1813]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 143, fig. 720-723](#).
- [JH] *Hesperia alveus* Duponchel, 1832. In: Godart, Hist. nat. Lépid. suppl. 1: [259-260](#).
TL: Provence (S France) ; nec Hübner, [1803]. Samml. eur. Schmett. 1: [pl. 92, fig. 461-463](#).
- [JS] *Syrichthus alveus* f. *foulquieri* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. Lépid. comp. 4: [404-406, 680, pl. 56, fig. 487-489](#).
TL: Saint Zacharie (dep. Var, SE France).
- [JS] *Hesperia foulquieri* race *picena* Verity, 1920. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 32(1): [4](#).
TL: Sibillini Mts. (C Italy).
- [JS] *Hesperia foulquieri* f. *supra-bellieri* Verity, 1920. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 32(1): [4](#).
TL: S. France.
- [JS] *Hesperia bellieri* race *nigropicta* Verity, 1926. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 38(7-8): [103](#).
TL: Oulx, Cesana, Clavières. (Piedmont, NW Italy).
- [JS] *Pyrgus bellieri* var. *gaillardi* Picard, 1948. Lambillionea 48(5-6): 37.
TL: dep. Gard (S France).
- [JS] *Pyrgus bellieri* ssp. *adkini* Picard, 1948. Rev. fr. Lépidop. 11(15-16): 327.
TL: Bagnols-les-Bains (dep. Lozère, S France).
- [JS] *Pyrgus bellieri* ssp. *corsicae* Renner, 1991. Neue Entomol. Nachr. 28: [66, pl. 1, fig. 4, pl. 9, fig. 47-48](#).
TL: Evisa (Corsica, S France).

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) numida (Oberthür, 1910)

- [ORIG] *Syrichthus alveus* f. *numida* Oberthür, 1910. Étud. Lépid. comp. 4: [404-405](#), [680](#), [pl. 55, fig. 484-486](#).
TL: Tazoult (NE Algeria).

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) onopordi (Rambur, [1839])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia onopordi* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 13, p.](#) [1840]: 319-320.
TL: Granada (Andalusia, S Spain).
[JS] *Pyrgus conyzae* Guenée, 1877. Petites Nouv. Entomol. (2)9(175): [145](#).
TL: Voirons, Savoie (E France).
[JS] *Syrichthus onopordi quercii* Oberthür, 1912. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 6: [107](#), [345](#), [pl. 143, fig. 1328-1330](#).
TL: Polleca (Monti Aurunci, C Italy).
[IFS] *Hesperia onopordi* gen.II. *fulvotincta* Verity, 1919. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 31(2): [27](#).
TL: Firenze (Toscany, Italy).
[JS] *Hesperia onopordi* race *pallidissima* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [73-74](#).
TL: Sierra de Albarracin (Aragon, C. Spain).
[SN] *Hesperia onopordi* race *fulvotincta* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [74](#).
Stat. nov. for *Hesperia onopordi* gen.II. *fulvotincta* Verity, 1919.

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) carlinae (Rambur, [1839])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia carlinae* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 11, n.](#) [1840]: 314-315 (nota).
TL: Alps (France ; Switzerland).
[JS] *Syrichthus carlinae* f. *olivacea* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 4: [409](#), [680](#), [pl. 56, fig. 497-498](#).
TL: La Graves (dep. Hautes-Alpes, France).
[JS] *Hesperia carlinae* race *atrata* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(4): [57](#).
TL: Formazza Valley (Piedmont, NW Italy).
[JS] *Pyrgus carlinae* ssp. *ochroides* Kauffmann, 1951. Mitt. Schw. Entomol. Ges. 24(4): [352](#).
TL: Val Bedretto (Ticino, Switzerland).
[JS] *Pyrgus carlinae* race *cottiana* Kauffmann, 1955. Boll. Soc. Entomol. It. 84: [139-140, fig. 2](#).
TL: Cottian Alps (NW Italy).

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) cirsii (Rambur, [1839])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia cirsii* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 12, o.](#) [1840]: 315 (nota).
TL: Fontainebleau (C. France).
[auct] *Papilio fritillum* [Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775. Ankündigung syst. Werkes Schmett. Wienergegend: [159](#).
TL: Vienna (Austria).
[JS] *Scelothrix cynarae* var. *iberica* Grum-Grshimailo, 1893. Horae Soc. Entomol. Ross. 27(3-4): [384-385](#).
TL: Spain.
[JS] *Syrichthus cirsii* var. *herrichii* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 4: [410](#), [681](#), [pl. 56, fig. 508](#).
TL: Sierra Alta (prov. Teruel, Spain).

- [JS] *Syrichtus armoricanus* var. *fabressei* Oberthür, 1910. Ét. Lépid. Comp. 4: [412](#), [681](#), [pl. 57, fig. 518-520](#).
TL: Sierra Alta (prov. Teruel, Spain).
- [JS] *Hesperia fritillum* f. *parafabressei* Verity, 1925. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 37(5): [72](#).
TL: Digne (SE France).
- [JS] *Pyrgus fritillum* ssp. *turcivola* Lattin, 1950. Istanb. Univ. Fen Fak. Mecm. (B)15(4): 326, pl. 2, fig. 6.
TL: Nemrut Dagi (prov. Bitlis, E Turkey).
- [JS] *Pyrgus cirsii* ssp. *tramelanensis* Kauffmann, 1951. Mitt. Schw. Entomol. Ges. 24(4): [354-355](#).
TL: Schweizer Jura (Switzerland).

Pyrgus (Ateleomorpha) cinarae (Rambur, [1839])

- [ORIG] *Hesperia cinarae* Rambur, [1839]. Faune entomol. Andal. 2: [pl. 8, fig. 4-5, j](#).
TL: Sarepta (Volga reg., Russian Federation).
- [JH] *Hesperia cynarae* Boisduval, 1840. Gen. Ind. Meth. Eur. Lepid.: [36](#).
TL: Taganrok (Russian Federation).
- [JS] *Hesperia cinarae* ssp. *clorinda* Warren, 1927. Entomol. Rec. J. Var. 39(6): [81-82](#).
TL: Tragacete (prov. Cuenca, C Spain).
- [JS] *Hesperia cinarae* f. *atrata* Thurner, 1938. Mitt. Naturwiss. Inst. Sofia 11: [137, fig.](#)
TL: Petrino (S North Macedonia).

Conclusion

This synonymic list offers a foundation for the taxonomy of Western Palearctic Hesperidae.

By linking each name to its original description, it enhances transparency, accessibility, and historical accuracy. However, the list is not yet complete, and gaps remain in both hyperlinks and taxonomic data. Researchers, lepidopterists and enthusiasts are warmly invited to contribute by submitting missing hyperlinks, overlooked synonyms, or other relevant information.

Author contribution

Michel Taymans: conceptualisation, analysis, visualisation, writing - original draft, writing – review and editing.

Sylvain Cuvelier: analysis, validation, visualisation, writing – review and editing.